

Pre-Survey

Student Name: _____ Student ID: _____

Instructions: This questionnaire gives you the opportunity to provide background information on your prior experience working on group projects and communication with other students at the university. Please fill out the questions below.

1. What best describes your gender?
 - a. Female
 - b. Male
 - c. Prefer not to say
 - d. Prefer to self-describe: _____

2. Please provide the number of group projects (3+ students) you have previously participated in.

3. How were these groups formed (group formed by the lecturer or by students).

4. What is your level of satisfaction with the team in your last project?

5. Are role models important for your discipline choices?
 - a. Don't know
 - b. Not important
 - c. Not very important
 - d. Somewhat important
 - e. Very important

6. Have you experienced gender bias in the School of Computer Science?
 - a. No
 - b. Don't know
 - c. Yes, positive and negative
 - d. Yes, mostly positive
 - e. Yes, mostly negative

7. Does gender imbalance affect you at meetings or discussions with other students?
 - a. Don't know
 - b. Not at all
 - c. Not really
 - d. To some extent
 - e. Yes

8. Do you believe the “boy’s club” mentality is present in the classroom.
 - a. Don’t know
 - b. Not at all
 - c. Not really
 - d. To some extent
 - e. Yes

9. I am mindful of my communication approach in the classroom.
 - a. Strongly Disagree (1)
 - b. Disagree (2)
 - c. Neutral (3)
 - d. Agree (4)
 - e. Strongly Agree (5)

10. I wait to be acknowledged prior to speaking to others.
 - a. Never (1)
 - b. Rarely (2)
 - c. Sometimes (3)
 - d. Very Often (4)
 - e. Always (5)

11. I feel welcome while attending social events with other students.
 - a. Strongly Disagree (1)
 - b. Disagree (2)
 - c. Neutral (3)
 - d. Agree (4)
 - e. Strongly Agree (5)

12. At school, I am interrupted when I am speaking.
 - a. Never (1)
 - b. Rarely (2)
 - c. Sometimes (3)
 - d. Very Often (4)
 - e. Always (5)

13. I have received verbal abuse in the classroom.
 - a. Strongly Disagree (1)
 - b. Disagree (2)
 - c. Neutral (3)
 - d. Agree (4)
 - e. Strongly Agree (5)

14. The behavior of other students has sometimes made me feel uncomfortable.

- a. Strongly Disagree (1)
- b. Disagree (2)
- c. Neutral (3)
- d. Agree (4)
- e. Strongly Agree (5)